

Geliş Tarihi: 24.11.2021
Kabul Tarihi: 19.01.2022
Yayın Tarihi: 31.01.2022

PHASELIS

VIII (2022) 17-25
DOI:10.5281/zenodo.5922036
journal.phaselis.org

Phaselis' Land Snails

Phaselis'in Karasal Salyangozları

Aydın ÖRSTAN* & M. Zeki YILDIRIM**

Abstract: A survey conducted during the years 2019 and 2021 in Phaselis found 22 species of snails and one species of semi-slug. The most abundant taxa were *Albinaria lycica phaselis*, *Metafruticola schuberti*, *Orculella ignorata* and *Rumina saharica*. The scarcity of larger snails (*Cornu*, *Eobania* and *Zonites* species) was noteworthy. The anatomy of a specimen of *M. schuberti* from Phaselis is presented and the differences observed in comparison to the previously published anatomy of the species are pointed out. A dimensional analysis is used to separate the *Rumina* specimens into two species as *R. saharica* and *R. decollata*. An unidentified *Vitrea* species collected in Phaselis and elsewhere in southwestern Turkey that is characterized by the spiral lines present on its shells is also discussed.

Keywords: Gastropod, Taxonomy, Archaeomalacology, Biodiversity

Öz: Bu çalışma 2019 ve 2021 yıllarında Phaselis'de yapılmış olup, araştırma sonunda 22 salyangoz türü ile bir adet yarı sümüklü böcek türü tespit edilmiştir. En bol bulunan türler *Albinaria lycica phaselis*, *Metafruticola schuberti*, *Orculella ignorata* ve *Rumina saharica*'dir. Türkiye genelinde yayılış gösteren bazı büyük boyutlu salyangozların (*Cornu*, *Eobania* ve *Zonites* cinslerine ait türler) araştırma sahasındaki azlığı dikkat çekicidir. Araştırmada Phaselis'ten toplanılmış *M. schuberti*'nin anatomisi sunulmakta olup, tür üzerinde daha önceden yayınlanmış anatomik bulgulara göre farklılıklara dikkat çekilmiştir. *Rumina* örneklerini iki türe (*R. saharica* ve *R. decollata*) ayırmada boyutsal analiz kullanılmıştır. Phaselis ve güneybatı Türkiye'nin başka lokalitelerinden toplanan ve kabuklarında belirgin sarmal çizgiler bulunan *Vitrea* örnekleri de kısaca tartışılmıştır.

Anahtar sözcükler: Gastropod, Taksonomi, Arkeomalakoloji, Biyolojik Çeşitlilik

Introduction

Phaselis was a well-known harbor city in southwestern Turkey that was inhabited approximately between VIIIth century BC to XIIIth century AD¹. The present day ruins of the city lie on a small promontory at the Mediterranean coast 40 km south of the city of Antalya. The city proper occupies mostly flat and sandy ground with a slightly elevated (< 30 m) acropolis facing the sea. Along the coastline there are beaches extending to the north and the south. A cemetery complex on a steep

* Research Associate, Dr., Section of Mollusks, Carnegie Museum of Natural History, Pittsburgh, Pennsylvania, U.S.A.; anothermail@hotmail.com | <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2167-5694>

** Prof. Dr., Mehmet Akif Ersoy Üniversitesi, Bucak Sağlık Yüksek Okulu, Burdur, Turkey. | <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0281-2232>

¹ Arslan & Tüner Önen 2016.

hillside to the north of the promontory is separated from the city by a flat gap of about 100 m. This gap, now occupied by a road and a parking lot, was once the mouth (now canalized under the road) of a short lagoon extending to the west. The areas outside the ruins are mostly wooded where the dominant tree species is the black pine (*Pinus nigra*). The hills surrounding the city consist of both volcanic and calcareous rocks². The ruins of the city are marble and limestone.

The limestone areas of southwestern Turkey are known to have a rich land snail fauna³. Likewise, the diversity of land snails in and around Phaselis would also be expected to be relatively high. There are already a number of land snail records from Phaselis scattered in the literature. The ones we are aware of are for *Lindholmiola gyria*⁴, *Pleurodiscus balmei*⁵, *Oxychilus cyprius*⁶, *Orculella ignorata*⁷ and *Metafruticicola schuberti*⁸. Furthermore, one taxon described in 1993, *Albinaria lycica phaselis*, bears the name of the city⁹. However, no comprehensive list of the land snail species of Phaselis has been published until now. We present here the findings of a 3-day land snail survey that we carried out in Phaselis.

Materials and Methods

The survey took place in three stages. The first stage on 13 June 2019 was carried out by the first author over about three hours. It covered only the main ruins including the acropolis hill. The second stage on 14 June 2021 was also carried out by the first author and lasted about one and a half hours. It covered only the main ruins. The third and the last stage of the survey took place on 8 September 2021 and consisted of three parts. The first part was carried out by both authors and one additional person in the north slope (cemetery) over about an hour. The second and the third parts, lasting about 30 min each, were carried out by both authors in the main ruins and at the cliff above the Hellenistic temple west of the cemetery, respectively. The distance between the farthest stations of the survey was about 700 m and the total area covered is estimated to be approximately 60,000 m². We took only the shells that were loose on the ground or in top soil. To avoid disturbing the archaeological record, shells embedded in wall remains, primarily *Rumina*, were photographed but not removed. Small volumes of loose soil were also taken, sieved into fractions and sorted for small shells. Other than the semi-slug *Daudebardia*, whose shells were found, the survey did not include slugs that may be present in the survey area. All species names follow Molluscabase (<https://molluscabase.org/>).

We measured the genitalia of *Metafruticicola schuberti* on photographs using ImageJ (<https://imagej.nih.gov/ij/>). We also measured the genitalia of *M. schuberti* from the island of Ro (southwest of Kaş) on its published photograph¹⁰ and those of *M. hikmeti* on Hudec's¹¹ drawing. The whorls of the *Rumina* shells were counted starting from the aperture. Thus, the first whorl is the whorl above the aperture (the body whorl) and its diameter (D1) as measured here excludes the aperture, while D3 is the diameter of the third whorl above the aperture. The number of ribs (per 0.5 mm) on the ventral penultimate whorl¹² of eight *Truncatellina* shells (selected to establish the

² Colin 1962.

³ Neubert *et al.* 2000; Örstan 2019.

⁴ Maassen 1991.

⁵ Bank & Menkhorst 1991.

⁶ Riedel 1995, 50.

⁷ Hausdorf 1996.

⁸ Bank *et al.* 2013, 96.

⁹ Nordsieck 1993.

¹⁰ Mylonas *et al.* 2019.

¹¹ Hudec 1971, Fig. 3.

¹² Kneubühler *et al.* 2020.

limits of the rib density range) were counted under a microscope. Representative lots of seven species collected during the survey have been deposited in the Carnegie Museum of Natural History, Pittsburgh, PA, U.S.A. (CM 177526-177532). A reference collection consisting of at least one specimen of the larger species will be given to the Phaselis Research Station.

Results and Discussion

Some boulders seen at the cemetery area appeared to be of volcanic origin, but small natural rock fragments from the base of the cliff above the temple effervesced with hydrochloric acid indicating that the base rock at that locality was calcareous. These observations agree with a previous study that indicated that both volcanic and calcareous rocks were present in the general area¹³.

The first stage of the survey in June 2019 found 18 species. The second stage in June 2021 started soon after a rainstorm while the ground was still wet, but the only active snails seen were *Eobania vermiculata* and *Metafruticicola schuberti* (Fig. 1). The former was a new record that brought the species total to 19. The third stage in September 2021 added four new species to the list (*Caracollina lenticula*, *Mastus rossmaessleri*, *Pagodulina pisidica* and *Zonites beydaglariensis*) all of which were from the areas (cemetery and the cliff above the temple) that had not been surveyed during the first and the second stages.

Fig. 1. Live snails observed at Phaselis after a rainstorm on 14 June 2021. A. *Eobania vermiculata*. B. *Metafruticicola schuberti*

The determination of whether or not a survey has found all of the snail species present in an area is a problem with no easy solutions¹⁴. Despite the addition of four new species during the last stage of the survey, we believe that the present total of 23 is close to the actual number of shelled gastropod species that are present in Phaselis and that future work will not increase the species total significantly unless the survey boundaries are expanded. For southwestern Turkey in general, this number represents a relatively high diversity of gastropods for a rather small area and a linear separation of 700 m. In comparison, Neubert *et al.*¹⁵ listed 35 species over a linear distance of about 35 km for the area between Kaş and Beymelek.

The following list gives the 22 species and subspecies of snails and one species of semi-slug found during the survey.

¹³ Colin 1962.

¹⁴ Cameron & Pokryszko 2005.

¹⁵ Neubert *et al.* 2000.

Albinaria lycica phaselis (Nordsieck 1993)
Caracollina lenticula (Michaud, 1831)
Cecilioides veneta (Strobel, 1855)
Cornu aspersum (Müller, 1774)
Daudebardia rufa (Draparnaud, 1805)
Eobania vermiculata (Müller, 1774)
Granopupa granum (Draparnaud, 1801)
Lindholmiola gyria (Roth, 1839)
Mastus rosmaessleri (Pfeiffer, 1847)
Metafruticicola schuberti (Roth, 1839)
Pagodulina pisidica (Schütt, 1993)
Orculella ignorata (Hausdorf, 1996)

Oxychilus cyprius (Pfeiffer, 1847)
Paralaoma servilis (Shuttleworth, 1852)
Pleurodiscus balmei (Potiez & Michaud, 1838)
Punctum pygmaeum (Draparnaud, 1801)
Rumina decollata (Linnaeus, 1758)
Rumina saharica Pallary, 1901
Rupestrella rhodia (Roth, 1839)
Truncatellina cf. cylindrica (Férussac, 1807)
Vitrea sp.
Xeropicta derbentina (Krynicky, 1836)
Zonites beydaglariensis (Riedel, 1982)

The most abundant species in Phaselis were *Albinaria lycica phaselis*, *Metafruticicola schuberti*, *Orculella ignorata* and *Rumina saharica*. The shells of *Albinaria* and *Rumina* were present often in large numbers along the bases of the walls of the various building remains.

A curious finding of our survey was that the shells of large snail species were sparse in Phaselis. The large species that we had expected to find included *Zonites beydaglariensis*, a native snail common between Demre and the ruins of Olympos (southwest of Phaselis), and the nonnative *Cornu aspersum* and *Eobania vermiculata*. *Zonites beydaglariensis* was represented by only two fresh juvenile shells found during the third stage of the survey. *Cornu aspersum* and *E. vermiculata* are both edible

Fig. 2. Comparison of the only intact *Cornu aspersum* shell from Phaselis (bottom) with the shells of the same species at different stages of aging (top row). The Phaselis shell still retains traces of its bands and comes closest to the fourth shell in the top row. The shells in the top row were from a roadside location near Kuşadası, Aydın

snails usually present among the ruins of ancient cities. Such present-day colonies may include the descendants of those snails that may have been brought as food during the periods when the cities were inhabited. In Phaselis, only one intact, but weathered shell of *C. aspersum* and the fragments of another were found. The intact shell was found partially buried in soil near the Gate of Hadrian. The comparison of this shell with recent shells of *C. aspersum* at various stages of weathering collected elsewhere (Fig. 2) shows that the Phaselis shell has lost almost all of its periostracum although its bands are still visible faintly. During field experiments, empty shells of *C. aspersum* exposed to sunlight during summer months started to lose their colors and periostraca within 3 months¹⁶. We do not know the climatic conditions the Phaselis shell has experienced, but we estimate that it is several years old but not old enough to have been from the period when the city was inhabited. The lack of any fresher shells of *C. aspersum* in Phaselis is somewhat unusual.

Eobania vermiculata presents another puzzle. This species was not found in June 2019, but after a rainstorm in June 2021, live individuals were seen crawling on the walls near the remains of the aqueduct (Fig. 1A). One fresh empty shell was also found in the same area. But when we searched for the species around the aqueduct in September 2021, no dormant snails or empty shells of it

¹⁶ Menez 2002.

were found. On dry days *E. vermiculata* estivates attached to walls, rocks and tree trunks and, being a relatively large snail, is spotted easily. Thus, had dormant snails been present on or around the aqueduct in September 2021 we would have noticed them. We have no explanation for why we could find *E. vermiculata* on only one of the three survey days.

Below are additional remarks on some of the species found during the survey.

Metafruticicola schuberti:

This is a very common and often abundant species along the coastal areas of southwestern Turkey with a previous record from Phaselis¹⁷. The *Metafruticicola* shells from Phaselis are similar

Fig. 3. *Metafruticicola schuberti* shells from Phaselis (left) and the type locality of the species (right). Both shells were 18.5 mm in diameter

to the *Metafruticicola* shells from the type locality¹⁸ (Fig. 3). We have dissected one *Metafruticicola* specimen from Phaselis (Fig. 1b, 4) and compared its genitalic anatomy to the published descriptions of the genitalia of *M. schuberti* from the island of Ro southwest of Kaş¹⁹ and *M. hikmeti*, described by Hudec from Side, east of Antalya²⁰. The latter species is considered to be a junior synonym of *M. schuberti*²¹. The length ratios of various parts of the genitalia of the Phaselis specimen differ slightly from those calculated for the published descriptions. The epiphallus to penis ratios of both *M. schuberti* from Ro and *M. hikmeti* (1.8-1.9) are larger than that of the Phaselis specimen (1.5). Likewise, the flagellum to penis ratios of *M. schuberti* from Ro (3.9) and *M. hikmeti* (4.4) are larger than that of the Phaselis specimen (3.3). In both *M. schuberti* from Ro and *M. hikmeti* the free oviduct is longer than the vagina with length ratios of 7 and 2.2, respectively; while in the Phaselis specimen the free oviduct is shorter than the vagina with a ratio of 0.6. In addition, the relative lengths of the penile verges (papillae) of these specimens differ. The length of the penile verge of the Phaselis specimen is about 0.3 times the penis length (Fig 4B). In contrast, the length of the verge of *M. schuberti* from Ro is about 0.7 times the penis length. Similarly, Hudec's²² drawing of the genitalia of *M. hikmeti* appears to show the faint outline of a verge inside the penis that is longer than one half the length of the penis. The taxonomic significance of these differences between the genitalia of these specimens will be reevaluated in a future publication after we have had a chance to dissect *M. schuberti* specimens from the type locality.

Rumina species: Two *Rumina* species occur in western Turkey usually near rural human habitats, agricultural fields and often also in ruins. The currently accepted names for these species are *Rumina saharica* for the one with narrower and somewhat cylindrical shells and *Rumina decollata* for the one with wider shells²³. We have found both types of shells at Phaselis (Fig. 5a).

¹⁷ Bank *et al.* 2013, 96.

¹⁸ Roth described *M. schuberti* (as *Helix schuberti*) in 1839 and gave its type locality as *In sepulcris necropoleos dictae "Cacamo"*, which translates as "in graves at necropolis called Cacamo" (Roth 1839, 15). Cacamo was a name used in the early 19th century European publications for the Kekova region around the village of Üçağız (Örstan 2019). The "necropolis" Roth referred to, hence the type locality, was most likely the collection of Lycian tombs along the eastern coast just outside of Üçağız.

¹⁹ Mylonas *et al.* 2019.

²⁰ Hudec 1971, 321.

²¹ Bank *et al.* 2013, 95.

²² Hudec 1971, Fig. 3.

²³ Bank & Gittenberger 1993.

Because both species lose (decollate) the earlier whorls of their shells more or less haphazardly, shell heights cannot be used reliably to separate the two species. However, a scatter plot of the diameter of the third whorl (D3) against the diameter of the first whorl (D1) provides a convenient way to separate the adult *Rumina* shells ($n=40$) collected at Phaselis into two groups (Fig. 5B). We are identifying the smaller shells ($D1 \leq 9$ mm, $D3 < 8.5$ mm) as *R. saharica* and the larger shells ($D1 \geq 9.5$ mm, $D3 > 8.5$ mm) as *R. decollata*. Some overlap between the dimensions of the two species is expected and the shells with D1 values in the range 9-10 mm and D3 values near 8.5 mm cannot easily be assigned to either species (no shells in that range have so far been found in Phaselis). An unusually large *R. decollata* shell was found in the Phaselis cemetery (Fig. 5).

Mastus rosmaessleri: We have identified the *Mastus* shells from Phaselis as *M. rosmaessleri* even though the Phaselis shells are noticeably smaller than those from the Kekova region where the species is quite common²⁴ (Fig. 6). Anatomical comparisons of specimens from different areas may lead to a revision of this identification in the future.

Truncatellina cf. cylindrica: Thirty-nine adult *Truncatellina* shells were collected at Phaselis. *Truncatellina* species are considered to be quite variable especially in shell dimensions and the variation observed in our sample is no exception. The length range of the sample was 1.40-1.94 mm (Fig. 7) and the rib density range of a selected subsample was 8-14 ribs/0.5 mm. Kneubühler *et al.* recently argued that there were no conchological criteria to distinguish the three *Truncatellina* species that they examined, *T. cylindrica*, *T. rothi* and *T. haasi*²⁵. The rib density range of the Phaselis sample falls within the range

Fig. 4a. Lower genitalia of the *Metafruticicola schuberti* specimen from Phaselis. B. Opened penis showing the penile verge. Abbreviations: BC, bursa copulatrix; E, epiphallus; F, flagellum; FO, free oviduct; P, penis; PV, penile verge; RP, retractor of penis; V, vagina; VD, vas deferens

Fig. 5a. Representative *Rumina* shells from Phaselis. Shell #1 is *R. saharica*, shells #2 and #3 are *R. decollata*. The unusually large shell #3 was from the cemetery area. B. Scatter plot of the two shell diameters for 40 adult *Rumina* shells from Phaselis. Arrow points at the marker for shell #3

²⁴ Örstan 2019.

²⁵ Kneubühler *et al.* 2020.

for *T. rothi*; however, Kneubühler *et al.* recommended that *T. rothi* be synonymized under *T. cylindrica*. These three species are considered to be toothless, but the Phaselis sample presents a complication: a small tooth is present on the inner edge of the columella in about 46% of the adult shells (Fig. 7, shell #3). Nevertheless, we are identifying the Phaselis shells tentatively as *T. cylindrica* pending the outcome of our continuing study of *Truncatellina* in southern Turkey.

Daudebardia rufa: Nine juvenile and broken adult shells of a semi-slug were collected during the survey. However, we found no live semi-slugs either in June 2021 when the ground was wet or in September 2021 when we overturned and examined several fallen trees in the pine grove immediately west of the city. Because *D. rufa* has been recorded from the Antalya area²⁶, we are identifying our specimens as *D. rufa*. However, the identification of *Daudebardia* species using their shells alone, especially when the specimens are incomplete or juveniles, is not always reliable and we will consider our identification tentative until a live specimen has been obtained and dissected.

Vitrea sp.: We have collected *Vitrea* shells at several localities in southwestern Turkey, including Phaselis, that differ from the known *Vitrea* species by the presence of spiral lines on them (Fig. 8-9). These shells resemble *Lindbergia karainensis*, a species that was first found in sediments of the Karain and Suluin caves located northwest of Antalya²⁷. We originally considered transferring *Lindbergia karainensis* to the genus *Vitrea* and identifying our specimens as *Vitrea karainensis*. But we have changed our opinion on advice from a reviewer. The arguments against our original intention are summarized as follows. First, *Lindbergia* was chosen tentatively for the placement of the specimens from Karain and Suluin, primarily because the shells were stated to have spiral lines on them and all the specimens available at the time of the description had been found in caves, those two traits being characteristics of *Lindbergia*. However, the extent of the spirals on *L. karainensis* shells is uncertain; the photographs of the holotype included in the original description do not show the surface microsculpture. Second, none of our specimens were from caves. Third, the primary distinction between the genera *Lindbergia* and

Fig. 6. Representative *Mastus rosmaessleri* shells from Phaselis (1, 2) and from the vicinity of Üçağız, Kekova region (3, 4). The heights of the shells #1 and #3 were 15.1 mm and 21.3 mm, respectively

Fig. 7. Representative *Truncatellina* shells from Phaselis. Shells #1 and #2 are the longest (1.94 mm) and the shortest (1.40 mm) specimens and shell #3 is a specimen with a columellar tooth (arrow).

Fig. 8. A shell of *Vitrea* sp. from Phaselis (diameter, 1.75 mm)

²⁶ Riedel 1995, 75.

²⁷ Rähle & Riedel 1987.

Vitrea is anatomical, but the anatomy of neither *L. karainensis* nor our specimens is known. Therefore, we are presently listing our specimens as *Vitrea* sp. A more detailed treatment of these snails, which will necessarily involve anatomical studies, is left for a future publication.

We believe that the results of our survey of the land snails of Phaselis is a significant contribution to the assessment of the general biodiversity of the area. We also hope that our findings will help with the interpretation of the archaeological findings. We intend to continue to work on the snails and slugs of Phaselis. Future work may not only add additional species, especially if the survey area is expanded, but may also lead to the resolution of some of the taxonomic issues that we have discussed here briefly. It is also our intention to include in our surveys the marine mollusks found along the coasts of Phaselis.

Acknowledgements

We thank Prof. Murat Arslan and Assoc. Prof. Nihal Tüner Önen for their support of and interest in our work without which this study would not have been possible. We also thank Eike Neubert and Francisco Welter-Schultes for their constructive reviews and for always being responsive to our requests for help with identifications, Tim Pearce for an informal review of the manuscript, Ayşe Yıldırım for collecting with us during the first part of the September 2021 survey and Beysun Örstan for her irreplaceable companionship during the survey trips.

Fig. 9. Close-up of a *Vitrea* shell from Phaselis showing the spiral microsculpture on the dorsal surface.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Arslan M. & Tüner Önen N. 2016, "Phaselis". Eds. H. İşkan & E. DüNDAR, *Lukka'dan Likya'ya, Sarpedon ve Aziz Nikolaos'un Ülkesi*. İstanbul, 300-317.
- Bank R. A. & Menkhorst P. M. G. 1991, "Bemerkungen über rezente Arten der Gattung *Pleurodiscus* (Gastropoda Pulmonata: Pupilloidea)". *Basteria* 55, 61-71.
- Bank R. A. & Gittenberger E. 1993, "Neither *Rumina truncata*, nor *R. gracilis*, but *R. saharica* (Mollusca: Gastropoda Pulmonata: Subulinidae)". *Zoologische Mededelingen* 67, 525-527.
- Bank R. A., Gittenberger E. & Neubert E. 2013. "Radiation of an eastern Mediterranean landsnail genus: revision of the taxa belonging to *Metafruticicola* von Ihering 1892 (Gastropoda, Pulmonata: Hygromiidae)". *Archiv für Molluskenkunde* 142, 67-136.
- Cameron R. A. D. & Pokryszko B. M. 2005. "Estimating the species richness and composition of land mollusc communities: Problems, consequences and practical advice". *Journal of Conchology* 38, 529-547.
- Colin H. J. 1962. "Fethiye-Antalya-Kaş-Finike (Güneybatı Anadolu) bölgesinde yapılan jeolojik etüdüler". *Maden Tetkik ve Arama Dergisi* 59, 19-60.
- Hausdorf B. 1996. "Die Orculidae Asiens (Gastropoda: Stylommatophora)". *Archiv für Molluskenkunde* 125, 1-86.
- Hudec V. 1971. "Helicidae (Gastropoda, Pulmonata) gesammelt von der niederländischen biologischen expedition in die türkei in 1959. *Zoologische Mededelingen* 45, 313-323.
- Kneubühler J., Baur H. & Neubert E. 2020. "Deception in taxonomy – the example of *Truncatellina rothi* (Hesse, 1916) (Pupilloidea: Truncatellinidae)". *Basteria* 84, 146-154.
- Maassen W. J. M. 1991. "Helicodonta gyria wilhelminae nov. subspec. von der griechischen Insel Kreta (Gastropoda Pulmonata: Helicidae)". *Basteria* 55, 123-126.
- Menez A. 2002. "The degradation of land snail shells during the annual dry period in a Mediterranean climate". *Iberus* 20, 73-79.
- Mylonas M., Vardinoyannis K. & Poulakakis N. 2019. "A contribution to knowledge on the terrestrial malacofauna of the Kastellorizo (Megisti) island group (SE Greece)". *Journal of Biological Research-Thessaloniki* 26: 13. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40709-019-0107-9>
- Neubert E., ÖRSTAN A. & WELTER-SCHULTES. F. 2000. "The land snails of the area between Kaş and Demre, southwestern Turkey, with special reference to *Albinaria* (Gastropoda, Pulmonata, Clausiliidae)". *Basteria* 64, 105-123.
- Nordsieck H. 1993. "Türkische Clausiliidae, I: Neue Arttaxa des Genus *Albinaria* Vest in Süd-Anatolien (Gastropoda: Stylommatophora)". *Stuttgarter Beiträge zur Naturkunde, Serie A* 499, 1-31.
- ÖRSTAN A. 2019. "The limited range of *Albinaria latelamellaris* in southwestern Turkey with the description of a new subspecies (Gastropoda, Pulmonata, Clausiliidae)". *Basteria* 83, 29-32.
- Rähle W. & Riedel A. 1987. "Eine neue, unterirdisch lebende Zonitiden-Art (Gastropoda: Stylommatophora) aus Südwestanatolien, Türkei. *Zoologische Mededelingen*, 61, 203-207.
- Riedel A. 1995. "Zonitidae sensu lato (Gastropoda, Stylommatophora) der Türkei. Übersicht der Arten. *Fragmenta Faunistica* 38, 1-85.
- Roth J. R. 1839. *Molluscorum species, quas in itinere per Orientem facto comites clariss. Schuberti doctores M. Erdl et J. R. Roth collegerunt*. München.